

Opponent processing in the retinal mosaic of Nymphalid butterflies

Primož Pirih, Marko Ilić, Andrej Meglič, Gregor Belušič

Electronic Supplementary material

Table of Contents

S1 Technicalities of rhodopsin spectroscopy & template fitting.....	2
S2 Basic opponent classes, stimulation aperture and stimulation intensity.....	4
S3 Spectral and polarisation analysis of the opponent pairs, linear opponency model.....	5
S4 Detailed analysis of stimulus response functions.....	7
S5 Anatomy of <i>Charaxes</i> compound eye.....	8
S6 Spectral and polarisation properties of photoreceptors in <i>Danaus</i> , <i>Morpho</i> , <i>Archaeoprepona</i>	9

S1 Technicalities of rhodopsin spectroscopy & template fitting

Table of fit parameters

R – rhodopsin peak wavelength; **M** – metarhodopsin peak wavelength; **c** – R/M peak absorbance ratio; **b** – baseline; σ – standard deviation of the mean of the parameters obtained from four experiments on a single animal

	<i>Charaxes</i>	R543	M502		<i>Apatura</i>	R526	M496	
Free parameters:	R, M	R, M, b	R, M, c	R, M, b, c	R, M,	R, M, b	R, M, c	R, M, b, c
R (nm)	542.5	542.4	543.9	543.5	527.3	521.4	516.1	512.6
σ_R	0.71	5.52	0.50	4.00	1.27	2.82	3.34	1.27
M (nm)	502.6	502.3	501.4	501.6	495.5	497.1	505.4	505.2
σ_M	0.69	3.30	1.24	1.90	1.05	0.80	4.43	3.80
c	(1.25)	(1.25)	1.27	1.26	(1.25)	(1.25)	1.08	1.07
σ_c			0.010	0.039			0.059	0.046

Figure S1: Spectroscopic determination of LW rhodopsin in *Apatura ilia* and *Charaxes jasius*

(a) Time traces of the eyeshine reflectance change (6 coloured traces, measured at the wavelengths designated in (b), the trace corresponding to the isosbestic point is shown in *yellow*); filtered data is shown as white traces; waterfall y-axis [400:700 nm].

(b) Reflectance spectra measured 0.25 s apart (5 coloured traces); filtered data (*white traces*); instrumental background (*yellow trace*).

(c) $U_1(\lambda)$ components (*black Z-shaped traces*) obtained from four experiments, sixteen fit curves (4 experiments \times 4 models), fit errors (*coloured traces at the bottom*), and $U_2(\lambda)$ components (*coloured traces at the top*). Fit errors show a consistent bias below 430 nm, possibly due to using inadequate templates, due to interference from SW opsins, or due to the complications arising from the intricacies of the optical measurement, signal processing, or the eye optics itself.

(d) Temporal components $V(t)$ of SVD-decomposed absorbance spectra, multiplied by signal energies obtained from the diagonal matrix D . V_1 has a course consistent with a first-order exponential relaxation. V_2 exhibits a small exponential relaxation, faster than V_1 , and is perhaps due to isomerisation of SW rhodopsins. V_3 is negligible. The energy of the first component is dominating, and is proportional to the absorbance difference change in a particular experiment, which in turn depends predominantly on the dark adaptation interval used between the experiments.

(e) Numerical estimates for R, M, baseline shift, and M/R peak ratio obtained from the four nested models. For *Charaxes*, all four models agree well. The free fit for M/R peak ratio confirms the biblical value 1.25. For *Apatura*, only the first two models (with constrained M/R ratio) are consistent.

(f) Templates obtained from the parameters estimated from the fits of the minimal model to the data. Rhodopsin templates (*green*), metarhodopsin templates (*blue*), absorbance difference (*magenta*), steady state metarhodopsin fraction $f_M(\lambda)$ (i.e. the fraction obtained upon sufficiently long illumination with monochrome light of wavelength λ), scaled as $y = 2f_M - 1$ (*cyan*); the associated normalised time constant of isomerisation $\tau(\lambda)$, scaled as $y = \frac{1}{2}(\log_{10} \tau/\tau_{\min}) - 1$; the y values [-1.0, -0.5, 0.0, 0.5, 1.0] correspond to $(\log \tau/\tau_{\min}) = [1, 10, 10^2, 10^3, 10^4]$ (*red*).

Apatura ilia

Charaxes jasio

S2 Basic opponent classes, stimulation aperture and stimulation intensity

Figure S2. Photoreceptor responses to spectral sweeps of light flashes

(a) U+G- and B+G- opponent receptors in *Apatura*

(b) Responses of a B+G- opponent receptor in *Charaxes* to sweeps with light intensity graded between $-3 \log(10^{-3})$ and $0 \log$ (full intensity); opponent signals are present already at the lowest intensity.

(c) Responses of a B+G- opponent receptor in *Charaxes* to two sweeps incident into a single ommatidium (2° aperture) and ~ 50 ommatidia (20° aperture); opponent signals are only slightly affected by the aperture angle of illumination.

Colour bars depict approximate human colours of stimuli, wavelengths in nm.

S3 Spectral and polarisation analysis of the opponent pairs, linear opponency model

Figure S3. Opponent combinations of U+G⁻, U+Y⁻, B+G⁻ and B+Y⁻ cells in *Apatura* (a-e) and *Charaxes* (f-m).

(a) Linear spectral sensitivity S of single U+G⁻ and B+G⁻ cells.

(b) Responses of cells in (a) to flashes through a rotating polarizer; oscillation at positive and negative voltages indicates responses of the main unit (UV⁺, B⁺) and opponent (G⁻) cells.

(c) PS of the opponent unit (G⁻) as a function of PS of the main unit (UV⁺, B⁺) in 13 UV+G⁻ and 8 B+G⁻ cells.

(d) U+G⁻ and B+G⁻ with low PS of the opponent unit can be explained by the diagonal SVF R5-R8 or all six SVF R3-8 converging on a single postsynaptic R1,2 cell. The PS of the summed opponent inputs is cancelled out.

(e) B+G⁻ cells with high PS and orthogonal orientation of the opponent unit are explained by horizontal R3,4 converging on a single vertical R1,2 cell. In this case, R1,2 and R3,4 could form polarization-opponent pairs, suitable for the analysis of polarized light.

(f) S of single U+G⁻, B+G⁻ and B+Y⁻ cells.

(g) Responses of cells in (f) to flashes through a rotating polarizer; oscillation at positive and negative voltages indicates responses of the main (U⁺, B⁺) and opponent (G⁻, Y⁻) cells.

(h) PS of opponent (G⁻, Y⁻) as a function of PS of main (U⁺, B⁺) cells. Scatterplot for 5 U+G⁻, 6 B+G⁻ and 2 B+Y⁻ cells.

(j, k) U+G⁻, B+G⁻ (j) and B+Y⁻ (k) with low PS of the opponent unit are explained by presynaptic R3-8 converging on a single postsynaptic R1,2 cell. The PS of the summed input of the opponent cells is cancelled out.

(l, m) Spectral sensitivities S_{B+G^-} and S_{B+Y^-} cells can be explained by linear subtraction of S_{OPP} of opponent cells from S of main cells.

Linear opponency model

Blue-sensitive cells in *Charaxes* have two different types of S curves in the opponent LW part. Maximal inhibition is either at ~560 nm or at 590 nm in class B+G⁻ and class B+Y⁻ cells, respectively.

We tested whether their S curves could be explained by a linear subtraction of S_{OPP} from S of the cells with silenced opponent signals. We isolated the S_B of the blue units (teal line in (l,m), average of 7 cells) by selectively adapting their opponents with monochrome green or orange light, and subtracted linearly scaled S_G (l; average of 23 cells) and S_Y (m; average of 13 cells), respectively:

$$S_{B+G^-} = S_B - 0.37 S_G + 0.20$$

$$S_{B+Y^-} = S_B - 0.30 S_Y + 0.12$$

The numerical difference (dashed line in m, l) closely matched the experimentally measured S_{B+G^-} and S_{B+Y^-} . The opponent signals in all but one B cells had PS~1, meaning that in B+G⁻ (j) and B+Y⁻ (k), multiple G or Y cells converge on single B cells.

The opponency can be explained as a functionality of single ommatidia that contain only class G or only class Y R3-8 receptors. We extend by assuming that R3-8 cells from class G, and R3-8 cells from class Y R3-8 are present in ‘non-red’ and red-reflecting ommatidia, respectively.

S4 Detailed analysis of stimulus response functions

Figure S4. Sensitivity of the photoreceptors in *Charaxes* and *Apatura*

(a,b) Relative light intensity, evoking half-maximal response (I_{50}) in the different spectral classes of photoreceptors in *Charaxes* (a) and *Apatura* (b). At log 0, flux is $I \approx 1.8 \times 10^{12}$ photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

(c,d) Relative light intensity, evoking half-maximal (I_{50}) opponent signals from the opponent units {G-, Y-, R-}, compared to the I_{50} of the main unit {U+, B+, G+} that were normalised to log 0.

In both species, units G- in the class U+G- are slightly more sensitive (0.1~0.2 log) than the main unit U+. In the other classes, the opponent units are less sensitive (~0.1 log in B+G-, ~0.9 log in G+R-).

S5 Anatomy of *Charaxes* compound eye

Figure S5: Light microscopical images of semithin sections.

(a) Longitudinal section; **CO**, cornea; **RE**, retina; **BM**, basement membrane; **LA**, lamina; red rectangle magnified in (d).

(b) Cross section at 214 μm. Receptor identity indicated by numbers; asterisk indicates rhabdom; **SPC**, secondary pigment cells.

(c) Cross section at 478 μm. Receptor identity is indicated with *numbers*; asterisk * indicates the rhabdom. At this level, R1&2 are axons and do not contribute to the rhabdom; R9 is dark and bilobed.

(d) Longitudinal section, indicated with red rectangle in (a). **SPC**, secondary pigment cells; **R9**, basal receptor R9; **Tap**, tracheolar tapetum; **BM**, basement membrane; **Tae**, taenidia; **Ax**, receptor axon.

(e) Length of the basal receptor R9 in 63 ommatidia.

Scale bar, (a) 500 μm, (b,c) 5 μm, (d) 20 μm.

High resolution image available at <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.14458893.v1>

S6 Spectral and polarisation properties of photoreceptors in *Danaus*, *Morpho*, *Archaeoprepona*

Figure S6. Spectral and polarization sensitivity in the monarch, blue morpho and prepona (*Danaus plexippus*, *Morpho peleides*, *Archaeoprepona demophon*).

Receptor sensitivity maxima (λ_{max} in nm) and polarization sensitivities are indicated at the bottom.

These species have an expanded lattice mosaic, the eyeshine exhibits red ommatidia. (For eyeshine images, see Belušič et al. 2021). Similar as in *Charaxes*, their retina contains the basic set of photoreceptor classes (U+G-, B+G-, G_{SVF}), and the expanded set with classes (B+Y-, Y, G+R-). The class U+Y- was not found, probably due to the small number of impaled class U photoreceptors.